

Determination Analysis of Career Planning to Employee Spirits in PT. Sinar Tamiang Medan

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ABSTRACT

This study purpose is to analyze the influence of experiential, educational, and achievement variables on spirit employee at PT.Sinar Tamiang Medan. The sampling technique used is a simple random sample technique where if the subject of study is less than 100 can be taken entirely to be sampled, with multiple linear analysis as a data processing tool. The results of this study show that simultaneously experiential, educational, variable and achievement have a positive and significant influence toward spirit employee. Yet partial only education and achievement that have a significant influence on employee morale, while experience has a positive but insignificant effect.

Keywords: Experience, Education, Achievement, Spirit Employee

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, human resources are very preferred in a company, because the existence of human resources in the company occupies an important position in the effort to reach the planned objectives. Therefore, the company must realize that the effort to achieve success depends not only on the abundance of human resources and technology, but also depends on the management of its people.

Career planning is the process of determining career objectives for employees and creating effectiveness in long-term development. Career planning differs from planning development to knowledge, expertise and attitudes (anonymous; 2008:2). "Career is sequence a position occupied by someone during his lifetime" (Simamora; 2010:85). Meaning someone

who starts working after a placement in an organization will continue to work for that organization during his active period until he or she enters the retirement age. Career development (career development) includes career management and career-planing. Planning a career is a process to decide what objectives will be pursued during the coming period and what will be done in order to achieve those objectives.

Every organization always strives to improve its employees ' work productivity. Therefore, leaders need to find ways and solutions to create a spirit of employee work. It is important because the spirit of work reflects deep pleasure on the work done so that faster work can be accomplished and better results can be achieved. According to Nitisemito (2010:161) The spirit of work is to do the job more actively so that the work can be expected faster and better. Meanwhile, Hasibuan (2011:94) said the spirit of work as the desire and sincerity of a person to work well and discipline to achieve maximum work achievement.

PT. Sinar Tamiang in terms of career planning strategy allows organizations to develop and place their employees in a position that suits their interests, needs and career objectives. PT. Sinar Tamiang in HR career management is very attentive to the career development of its employees. Career planning will support the effectiveness of employees and companies in achieving their objectives. In the implementation of career planning has not done well because there is a difference of salary between the central company and the branch company so that

employees feel reluctant to pursue a career and less eager to pursue a career in the branch company.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Career Planning

Sunyoto (2015:165) finalized career planning is a process that is passed by individual employees to identify and take steps to achieve his career goals. The realistic career scaffolding forces individuals to see existing opportunities in relation to their abilities. Career planning is a planning focused on work and identification of a career path that provides a logical progression of people among the work in the Organization (Mathis; 2011:343).

From some of the above sense it can be concluded that career planning is an ongoing process whereby individuals conduct work-world assessments, plan the steps to take to achieve those career choices, and make rational reasoning before making decisions about the desired career.

Career determinants

According Tohardi (2009:281) There are several factors that will affect the smooth presence of the career of a person or employee, namely:

1. Employer, co-worker and subordinate attitude
2. Experience
3. Education
4. Achievements

2. Working Spirit

According to Nitisemito (2010:161) The spirit of work is to do the job more actively so that the work can be expected faster and better. Sedangkan Hasibuan (2011:94) said the spirit of work as the desire and sincerity of a person to work well and disciplined to achieve maximum work achievement.

From the above definitions, it can be concluded that the spirit of work is the desire and sincerity of a person in doing work in a good and well-disciplined and high discipline to achieve maximum work achievement and also to achieve the

objectives that have been set by the company.

Factors affecting the spirit of work

According to Nitisemito in Tohardi (2009:292) Factors affecting the spirit of work are:

1. Adequate salary
2. Pay attention to spiritual needs
3. Need to create a relaxed atmosphere
4. Place employees in the right position
5. Safe and future feelings
6. Adequate facilities

METHOD

The type of research the authors use in this study is quantitative research that aims to know the relationship between two or more variables by research will then be able to build a theory that can serve to explain. Predict and control symptoms. (Rusiadi, 2013)

1. Population and samples/types and Data sources

a. Population

The population is a generalized region consisting of: objects/subjects that have specific qualities and characteristics set by research to be studied and then in conclusion (Sugiono; 2012:80). The population in this study is all employees of PT. Sinar Tamiang Medan, which amounted to 80 people.

b. Sample

According to Sugiyono (2014:84) The samples are part of the number and characteristics owned by the population. In this research the authors perform a non probability sampling sample withdrawal technique i.e. using saturated sampling because the entire population was made sample and the population number of 80 employees.

2. Data Analysis Techniques

The analysis of the data used is a quantitative analysis expressed by the numbers and the calculations Menggunakan standard methods assisted by the program Statistical Package Social Sciences (SPSS) version. The analysis used in this study was a double Linear regression

that previously carried out test escapes from the classical assumption.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

a. Data Quality Testing

1. Validity and Reliability Testing

a) Enforcement of Validity

Table 1 Item- Total Statistics

	Questions	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Description
Experience (X1)	1. The experience has helped in completing the work.	.643	Valid
	2. I always do the work according to the correct procedure	.362	Valid
	3. I always in front of professional in working	.485	Valid
	4. The work experience I have, help me accomplish the task efficiently.	.449	Valid
	5. I always put forward a professional attitude in work.	.477	Valid
	6. I do not waste working time with other activities that are not related to the work	.346	Valid
Education (X2)	1. My work in accordance with the background of the education I have	.559	Valid
	2. The higher the level of education will be more and more knowledge	.439	Valid
	3. The knowledge I have can be applied in my work	.687	Valid
	4. Positions or position that I have in accordance with my field of education	.449	Valid
	5. Previous works the training that supports the Educative brothers	.804	Valid
	6. Sustainable education (PPL) can improve skills and knowledge	.729	Valid
Achievements (X3)	1. In an effort to improve my work performance, the management of the company performs a fair assessment process.	.552	Valid
	2. The new employee who joined and the employees who have long joined in the company is treated equally by the company in the assessment process of work performance.	.331	Valid
	3. Work performance assessment conducted annually continuously	.370	Valid
	4. The results of a transparent work achievement will improve my ability to work in the future	.311	Valid
	5. Results from the assessment of the work achievement is reliable	.495	Valid
	6. My achievement is able to exceed the target	.522	Valid
The Spirit of work (Y)	1. I have a high spirit of work	.546	Valid
	2. I finish the job well and on time and in accordance with the job deadline	.587	Valid
	3. I never delay the job	.429	Valid
	4. I am able to complete more than one task in a day	.528	Valid
	5. I am happy with the work charged to me	.559	Valid
	6. Comfortable, clean, neat work environment and adequate facilities make the working passion of Mr/Mrs Increase	.485	Valid

b) Reliability Testing

Table 2 Recapitulation of Reliability Test Results Reliability Statistic

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of items	Description
Experience (X1)	.723	6	Reliabel
Education (X2)	.835	6	Reliabel
Achievements (X3)	.698	6	Reliabel
Spirits of Work (Y)	.775	6	Reliabel

From table above, SPSS known output results variables experience Cronbach's Alpha value of 0, 723 > 0.60, education variable 0, 835 > 0.60, achievement variables 0, 698 > 0.60, and variable work Spirit 0, 775 > 0.60. So that can be inferred all items submitted statements can be declared reliable or reliability.

2. Conformity test

a. Simultaneous Test (Test F)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	303.480	3	101.160	29.077	.000 ^b
	Residual	264.407	76	3.479		
	Total	567.887	79			
a. Predictors: (Constant), X3, X2, X1						
b. Dependent Variable: Y						

Based on it can be seen that the value $F_{\text{calculate}} = 29,077 > F_{\text{table}} = 2.72$ with a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$. From these results it can be concluded that experience, education and achievement simultaneously have significant effect on the spirit of work.

b. Partial/Individual Significant Trials (Test T)

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	3.696	2.244		1,647	.104		
	X1	.031	.183	.027	.171	.865	.249	4.014
	X2	.362	.093	.381	3.897	.000	.641	1.561
	X3	.419	.146	.428	2.875	.005	.277	3.613

Based on it can be seen that for each of the variables experience, education, achievement, towards the spirit of work is as follows.

The significance of the partial test is 5% (1 way), then the table can be calculated with the formula $DF = N - K - 1$, so that the tab is $DF = 80 - 4 - 1 = 75$ (1,992)

- 1) For X1, $T_{calculate} = 0,171 < T_{table} = 1.992$ with value sig. $0,865 > 0.05$.
Then X1 has no significant effect on Y
- 2) For X2 $T_{calculate} = 3,897 > T_{table} = 1.992$ with value sig. $0,000 < 0.05$
Then X2 significantly affects Y
- 3) For X3 $T_{calculate} = 2,875 > T_{table} = 1.992$ with a value of sig. $0,005 < 0.05$
Then X3 significantly affects Y

3. Coefficient of determination

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.731 ^a	.534	.516	1.86522
a. Predictors: (Constant), X3, X2, X1				
b. Dependent Variable: Y				

Based on the table above, the results of the R Square value of 0.534 as a double correlation value mean that experience, education, and achievement have a strong relationship with the spirit of work. The value of R Square represents the value of coefficient of determination, but in multiple regression it uses a Adjusted R Square value of 0.516 or 51.6%. Which means the variation of the work spirit is explained by 51.6 by experience, education, performance while the remaining $100\% - 51.6\% = 48.4\%$ are influenced by other variables that do not enter the model or are not researched such as, salary, and other environmental, etc.

CONCLUSION

1. $F_{calculate}$ value of $29,077 > F_{table} = 2.72$ with a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$
Then there is a simultaneous influence between experience, education and achievement of employee's working spirit at PT. Sinar Tamiang Medan.
2. Based on the results of the partial test (T)

- a. Test the influence of experience on the spirit based on variable test results
The value experience of $T_{Calculate} 0.171 < T_{Table} 1.992$ with significant $0.865 > 0.05$, the criteria of reject H_1 (accept H_0), means that partially there is no significant influence between experience on employee spirit at PT. Sinar Tamiang Medan
- b. Test the influence of education on the spirit of work
Based on variable test results The value Experience $T_{calculate} 3.897 > T_{Table} 1.992$ with a significant $0.000 < 0.05$, hence the criteria reject H_0 (accept H_1), it means that partially there is a significant influence between education to the employee's work spirit at PT. Sinar Tamiang Medan.
- c. Test the influence of achievement on the spirit based on variable test results
The value of $T_{calculate} 2.875 > T_{Table} 1.992$ with a significant $0.005 < 0.05$, then the criteria of reject H_0

(accept H_1), It means that partially there is a significant influence between the achievement of employee spirit at PT. Sinar Tamiang Medan.

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How to cite this article: Arifin D. Determination analysis of career planning to employee spirits in PT. sinar tamiang medan. International Journal of Research and Review. 2020; 7(6): 231-235.
